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EFFECTS OF DIGITALLY RECORDED PATIENT EDUCATION BEFORE
ESOPHAGEAL MANOMETRY PROCEDURE

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

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DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

High-resolution esophageal manometry (HREM) measures motility in patients with suspected esophageal disorders. Currently, the GI Motility Clinic's esophageal manometry patient educational tool is limited in explaining the process or expectations of the procedure. Patients presented for HREM have a baseline knowledge score of 56%, and 8 percent of procedures are aborted due to an elevated anxiety level. A literature review suggests a positive impact of recorded patient education before a procedure. An 8 minute patient educational recording was created to provide objective information about the esophageal manometry procedure.

The purpose of the digital recording is to 1) improve knowledge; 2) reduce procedural anxiety; 3) increase satisfaction, with aims of patient satisfaction scores to be consistently >95% and 4) reduce the percentage of patients aborting the HREM procedure secondary to anxiety in the GI Motility Clinic to be less than 2 percent.

A purposive, convenience sampling strategy was used and recruited 12 patients at baseline and 12 participants for implementation of the project. This project was set in the ambulatory GI Motility clinic within a tertiary hospital and multi-specialty academic health center in Southern California. Results demonstrated a significant increase in knowledge (from 58% to 95%) and reduction in anxiety post digitally recorded education. All participants liked the recorded education and there were zero aborted cases during the project implementation period. These findings suggested a positive

impact of the digitally recorded education as well as potential project success with implementation of digital education before esophageal manometry procedure. As the sample size on this project was very small, continued study with a larger sample size is needed.

Findings from this project support the larger body of evidence showing a positive impact of recorded patient education on patient outcomes. Furthermore, lessons learned from this project can be used to guide the development of recorded patient educational in other settings to provide a standardized means of patient education and improve patient outcomes.

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BACKGROUND

The primary function of the esophagus is to transport food from the mouth to the stomach. Synchronized contractions of the esophagus and appropriate relaxation of the lower esophageal sphincter (LES) are needed during each swallow for the successful passage of solids and liquid into the stomach. The lower esophageal sphincter is the ring-shaped muscle at the bottom of the esophagus that opens during swallows and closes in between or during fasting.

Esophageal dysmotility occurs when the esophagus fails to function properly. Currently, there are limited data on the incidence and prevalence of patients with esophageal dysmotility disorders. According to Gaumnitz (2017), within the spectrum of esophageal dysmotility conditions, achalasia is among one of the most often described motility disorders. Achalasia is a rare condition, which occurs when there is an abnormally low contractility or a lack of peristalsis of the esophagus and a failure of the LES to relax during swallowing. Achalasia results in food getting backed up in the esophagus. The incidence of achalasia is 1-3 cases per 100,000 population per year (Gaumnitz, 2017).

Currently, there is no cure for achalasia. Management approaches for achalasia generally include medical treatments with drugs like diltiazem, endoscopic pneumatic dilation, surgical Heller myotomy, and per-oral endoscopic myotomy (Ihara, Muta, Fukaura, & Nakamura, 2017). Based on the Chicago Classification (CC) version 3.0 of esophageal motility disorders, there are three main phenotypes or subtypes of achalasia: type I, II and III (2017). These subtypes are characterized by I) without esophageal peristalsis, II) presence of pan-esophageal pressurization, and III) with premature distal esophageal contractions (Kahrilas et al., 2014). The utilization of high-resolution

esophageal manometry (HREM) is crucial in determining which subtype of achalasia patient has, for the diagnoses as well as individualizing the best first-line therapy for the patient (Ihara et al., 2017).

HREM is a motility procedure used to measure motility function in patients with suspected esophageal disorders and aids in the diagnosis of muscular and neurologic disease. Currently, HREM is considered the golden diagnostic test for esophageal motility disorders (Rohof & Bredenoord, 2017). In addition to achalasia, HREM also aids in the diagnosis of esophago-gastric junction (EGJ) outflow obstruction, distal esophageal spasm, jackhammer esophagus, and minor motility disorder such as ineffective esophageal motility (Kahrilas et al., 2014).

During the HREM procedure, a thin, flexible catheter with multiple sensors is inserted through the patient's nose and passed down the esophagus, and into the stomach. Pressures are then recorded simultaneously from the stomach, LES, esophagus, and upper esophageal sphincter. To evaluate the motility of the esophagus, patients need to swallow saline water during the test; a total of ten complete swallows is necessary for the assessment of esophageal peristalsis. The procedure is done without any sedation so that he or she can follow commands. The patient needs to take sips of saline water and swallow to allow the evaluation with minimal risks for aspiration.

Problem Statement

An HREM is one of the few procedures the outpatient GI motility clinic offers to patients within the medical center, as well as patients referred by private, community gastroenterologists, surgeons, and local providers. Due to the variety of referral sources, it is unknown how much education and instructions patients have received about HREM

from their primary gastroenterologists or physician offices. From experience, patients' baseline knowledge is often limited across all referral sources. Currently, this clinic's esophageal manometry patient educational tool is a one-page generic form providing an overview of 1) indications for esophageal manometry, 2) preparation for the study, 3) as well as contacts for canceling or rescheduling the appointment. There is no specific information about how the procedure is conducted, what patients should expect, and what is required of them during the procedure.

Fear of the unknown is one of the three dimensions of preoperative anxiety and is suggested as a type of fundamental fear (Carleton, 2016). Often times, the patient reports anxiety before and during esophageal manometry. In some patients, the anxiety level remains high during parts or throughout the procedure. A lack of knowledge has been documented as a cause of pre-procedural anxiety in other medical procedures such as in patients before percutaneous coronary intervention (Mosleh et al., 2016). Many times, a higher anxiety level means longer procedure time as patients often have difficulty following commands to take sips of water and swallow. According to the pre-project data the GI motility clinic gathered from February to March 2020, in 8% of the time, procedures were aborted because patients were not able to complete the test due to a much-elevated anxiety level.

Understandably, anxiety can arise with a combination of factors including 1) meeting new providers; 2) undergoing an invasive procedure; and, 3) limited baseline knowledge. Despite the team's effort to provide guidance and support, it is the initial meeting and interaction with most of the newly referred patients. Likewise, the satisfaction scores reported within six months prior to implementation of this project

among patients undergoing esophageal manometry from August 2019 to January 2020 was 89%, which indicated that further improvement was needed.

Purpose Statement

The purpose of this doctoral quality improvement project was to develop a patient educational digital recording as an enhanced educational tool about HREM. The purpose of the recording is to 1) improve knowledge; 2) reduce procedural anxiety; 3) increase satisfaction, with aims of patient satisfaction scores to be consistently >95% on the organization's patient experience survey and 4) reduce the percentage of patients aborting the HREM procedure secondary to anxiety in the GI Motility Clinic to less than 2 percent.

Supporting Framework

Theories help provide a systematic framework as well as the reasoning for clinical practice (Christman & Cain, 2004). It is a usual practice for nurses and providers to prepare patients before procedures. However, the theoretical foundation of rationale to prepare patients for the physical sensations experienced as a basis for patient education, as well as the association between outcomes and care have not been routinely discussed or examined.

Self-Regulation Theory

Leventhal initially described how emotional and cognitive factors influence an individual's action plan or coping process while undergoing stressful healthcare events in the parallel response model, a precursor of the self-regulation theory (Cameron & Leventhal, 2008). Since 1983, Johnson tested and refined the structure and nature of the self-regulation theory (Johnson et al., 1997). The revised self-regulation theory as

illustrated in Figure 1, is based on the original parallel response model (Johnson et al., 1997). The self-regulation theory emphasizes two main processes of coping, one process at decreasing interference to functional activities and another process aims at reducing emotional response to the experience (Johnson, 1999).

Selection of Self-Regulation Theory for the Project

The Self-regulation theory provides fundamental principles as well as the rationale in providing patient education before a painful experience. Specifically, the self-regulation theory explains how patients use particular forms of information to manage different experiences; it also proposes that patients will elect to interpret and respond in ways that are consistent with their understanding of the healthcare experience (Johnson, Fieler, Jones, Wlasowicz & Mitchell, 1997; Johnson, 1999). The self-regulation theory has been chosen as a guiding framework as well as to provide support in the selection of information to be included in the creation of the esophageal manometry patient educational recording.

Components of the Model in Self-Regulation Theory

The two pathways within the model in self-regulation theory occur in an independent, parallel, dynamic, and cyclic process (Johnson, 1999). The process on the top row of the model is the functional pathway, which concerns regulating functional response with concrete, objective features of the experience and achieving functional goals (Sullivan-Bolyai et al., 2014). The emotional pathway at the bottom of the model focuses on regulating emotional responses with individual features of the event and attaining emotional goals (Johnson, 1999; Sullivan-Bolyai et al., 2014). The uniqueness

of this self-regulation theory is the idea of the two pathways for copings are independent of each other and have different outcomes (Johnson et al., 1997).

The top pathway supports problem-solving, which is derived from providing the patient with concrete, objective features of an impending healthcare event (Johnson et al., 1997). When physical features such as environmental characteristics, physical sensations, and temporal features of the experience predominate in cognitive reasoning; coping is then focused on those features (Sullivan-Bolyai et al., 2014). Next, individuals interpret the objective features by relating to past experiences or references, which then increase their confidence to cope with the current event by directing their focus at problem-solving (Johnson et al., 1997). The optimal outcome of the functional pathway is the ability to maintain usual activities; when patients can maintain usual activities, they are less likely to experience negative emotions (Johnson et al., 1997).

The bottom pathway of the model describes emotional response with attention directed toward subjective features. Subjective features are each patient's appraisal of the impending healthcare event (Johnson et al., 1997). Emotional memories may guide interpretation from past experiences. Patients are also disposed to experience the features if they were warned to anticipate them (Johnson, 1999). For example, if patients are warned about pain from a particular procedure, they would then likely experience pain. Coping in this pathway is directed at reducing emotional discomfort, which the individuals would select the emotional coping efforts that they believe will lessen such discomfort (Johnson et al., 1997). If an individual's coping effort results in the best outcome of being emotionally comfortable, the effectiveness of the emotional coping would then be feedback to the problem-solving pathway (Johnson et al., 1997).

Inter-relationships within Self-Regulation Theory

The reason the theory is called a self-regulation theory is that it is assumed that the meaning of each experience is unique to the individual patient and that each patient will decide how to manage the event and to cope in ways to achieve the desired outcomes (Johnson, 1999). Since the self-regulation model is a dynamic, self-motivated process, patients may choose to concentrate on one process at a time or they may switch back and forth between the two processes. Therefore, it is vital to assist patients on focusing attention on the objective, rather than subjective features of an experience (Johnson, 1999).

Earlier research suggests that if patients are not assisted in focusing their attention toward concrete features, patients often choose to concentrate on the emotional features of the experience such as pain, which could increase their negative emotional response (Johnson et al., 1997; Johnson, 1999). If self-management efforts are not effective in achieving emotional wellbeing, then the process would feedback to the earlier part of the emotional pathway to regulate the response and result in continued efforts for the patient to make changes and try coping again (Johnson et al., 1997; Johnson, 1999).

Figure 1. Model of information processing in self-regulation theory. Adaptation from Johnson, J. E., Fieler, V. K., Jones, L. S., Wlasowicz, G. S., & Mitchell, M. L. (1997). *Self-Regulation theory: Applying theory to your practice*. Pittsburgh, PA: Oncology Nursing Press. Permission to use is found in Appendix A.

Application of Self-Regulation Theory

Preparatory education with accurate descriptions of sensations patients may experience during painful stimulation has been associated with reduced emotional response and lower distress during a healthcare experience such as a diagnostic examination (Johnson, 1973). The self-regulation theory guides the selection of information to be used as patient education to assist patients to cope with stressful healthcare experiences (Johnson et al., 1997). For patients who reported some fear before surgery, providing objective information and coping interventions before procedures reduced patients' negative emotional reactions post-operatively (Johnson et al., 1997).

The self-regulation theory provides guidance and support in the creation of the esophageal manometry patient educational recording. According to Johnson et al. (1997), patients benefit when they are educated about the process and details of the impending procedural experience in concrete, objective terms before undergoing diagnostic tests. Concrete objective features include: 1) a narrative of the surrounding environment; 2) the sequence and duration of the event; 3) the physical sensations one may experience, and 4) explanation of the causes of such sensations or symptoms (Johnson, 1996).

Providing a narrative description of the procedural area such as a clinic room with a chair, stretcher, and cabinets on the wall, counters, and a sink helps to provide a cognitive image of the impending surrounding. Having a mental image of the impending environment can facilitate patients' retrieving of relevant information from memory, planning for coping strategies when it is time for the procedure, and assembling resources in achieving emotional comfort (Johnson, 1999).

Information involving temporal characteristics includes usual timing of the procedure, which in the case of esophageal manometry averages 4–7 minutes, with most patients completing the manometry in about 5 minutes. The procedure sequence is that the nurse will first assist the patient to sit up in a 90-degree upright position on the stretcher, followed by the application of lidocaine with a cotton swab to numb the nostril. Once the nostril is numbed, the physician will then insert the thin manometry catheter from the nose down to the esophagus. This temporal information helps patients focus attention on concrete objective features of the procedure as well as facilitate their interpretation of the experience.

Physical sensation includes descriptions of what patients may sense by seeing, hearing, touching, smelling, and tasting during the experience (Johnson et al., 1997). Tactile sensation related descriptors include pressure, tingling, aching, and numbness (Johnson, 1973). Words like painful, severe, distressing are not included in patient educational information as they describe patients' interpretation of their experiences subjectively and effort should be made to focus objectively (Johnson, 1973, Johnson, 1999).

The application of physical descriptors in the crafting of the esophageal manometry recording should avoid descriptions of how intense or distressing the procedure may be, as these subjective representations may predominate and lead patients to interpret and cope in terms of their vulnerability (Johnson, 1996). Because information serves as a resource for proactive coping, the education delivered can structure patients' expectations (Christman & Cain, 2004). For example, when subjective features dominate in the representation of pain, patients' attention will be directed to the

distress of painful stimulus and self-management of emotional responses to pain (Johnson, 1999). Instead, accurate, objective descriptors to be included in the recording should be a narrative of a cooling sensation when the cotton applicator touches the nostril. A feeling of numbness when the lidocaine is applied, as well as pressure in the nostril followed by irritation and pressure in the throat during manometry insertion should be described.

The process of the regulation of functional response can be further facilitated with concrete objective explanations of why the sensations were felt (Johnson, 1999). For example, throat irritation is felt because of the catheter being passed down the pharynx; followed by the sensation of pressure as the catheter reaches the lumen of the esophagus. Providing a rationale of the sensations experienced during the procedure enables patients to understand the experience and helps them to cope objectively. Reasoning directs the experience at problem-solving, rather than at emotional reactions (Johnson et al., 1997).

The most optimal outcome of the self-regulation theory is the patients' achievement of being both emotionally content as well as providing them with the ability to resume or maintain usual activities (Johnson et al., 1997). These are also the most desirable outcome for patients undergoing esophageal manometry, that patients can be emotionally comfortable; able to complete the procedure successfully without any complication, and to be discharged at their usual state of health.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Search Strategies

A literature review was conducted using databases: PubMed, CINAHL, Google Scholar, and PsychInfo. MeSH and key terms were used for the literature search, which included: disorders, esophageal dysmotility; recorded patient education, knowledge, anxiety, patient satisfaction, and Dr. Jean Johnson's Self-Regulation Theory. The search was restricted to include only scholarly journals published between 2014 - 2019 and in the English language except for literature relevant to the Self-Regulation Theory for which included the years from 1973 to 2019. Due to limited documentation available on the Self-Regulation Theory, no restriction was set on search date to allow all relevant documentation to be reviewed. The only exclusion criteria were research articles whose subjects were children.

Importance of a Literature Review

A literature review helps identify potential areas of research, provides context, and conveys ideas and knowledge that had been previously established in the literature. An effective literature review also compares prior studies or findings and help avoids duplicate research (Maggio, Sewell, & Artino, 2016).

Overview of the Function of the Esophagus

The primary function of the esophagus is to deliver food from the mouth to the stomach. In between swallows, the esophagus usually does not contract. Synchronized contractions of the esophagus and appropriate opening of the LES are needed during each swallow for the successful passage of solids and liquid into the stomach. The LES is a muscular structure at the bottom of the esophagus that opens after swallows and closes in between or during fasting. Symptoms of dysphagia with solids and or liquid, heartburn,

chest pain, globus sensation, and regurgitation can be signs of an underlying esophageal motor disorder.

Pathophysiology of Esophageal Motor Disorders

Achalasia is an uncommon, primary motor disorder of the esophagus with unknown cause (Ates & Vaezi, 2015). It is characterized by failure of the LES to completely relax along with a lack of esophageal peristalsis during swallowing (Ates & Vaezi, 2015). For this project, the focus of esophageal motility disorder will be on achalasia as it is the most commonly described esophageal motor disorder in the literature.

Patients with achalasia often present with symptoms of heartburn, chest pain, and regurgitation; and can often time be diagnosed with gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) especially after inconclusive esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD) or esophagram study (Khan, AlQaraawi, Al-Sohaibani, Al-Kahtani & Al-Ashgar, 2015). In comparison to patients with other esophageal motor disorder, patients with achalasia tend to have more extreme and frequent symptoms (Reddy, Patel, & Gyawali, 2017). In untreated achalasia patients, these symptoms are believed to be secondary to the fermentation of residual food trapped in the esophagus due to underlying impaired emptying of the esophagus rather than GERD (Khan et al., 2015). Since GERD is not the underlying etiology, some patients with achalasia response poorly to proton pump inhibitors (PPIs) and are often labeled with a diagnosis of refractory GERD (Khan et al., 2015). Exclusion of achalasia is essential before patients undergo anti-reflux surgery for the treatment of GERD.

Utility of HREM

Assessment of the underlying contractility and coordination of the esophageal muscle is crucial in the diagnosis of esophageal motor disorders. HREM is considered the best diagnostic test and is currently viewed as the gold standard for the assessment and evaluation of esophageal motor disorders (Rohof & Bredenoord, 2017). In addition to the assessment of GERD not responsive to PPI therapy, HREM has a broad application in the diagnosis of esophageal motor disorders such as distal esophageal spasm, nutcracker esophagus, ineffective esophageal motility, esophagogastric junction outflow obstruction, jackhammer esophagus, and achalasia.

Common Tests for Esophageal Motility Disorders

Esophagogastroduodenoscopy (EGD) is a procedure to examine the lining of the esophagus, stomach, and duodenum with a flexible endoscope. Endoscopic finding from EGD among patients with achalasia are often non-specific and may help in the diagnosis of achalasia in only one-third of patients (Ates & Vaezi, 2015). Therefore, the primary role of an EGD in the diagnosis of achalasia is to exclude any mechanical obstruction (Khan et al., 2015).

An esophagram is a test to evaluate the anatomy of the esophagus by the use of barium and X-rays. While the diagnosis of achalasia can be supported by esophagram findings such as dilation of the esophagus, tight esophagogastric junction, and delayed or poor emptying of the barium, results from an esophagram can be normal or non-diagnostic in up to a third of patients with achalasia (Ates & Vaezi, 2015). Similar to EGD, an esophagram is a poor diagnostic test for achalasia (O'Rourke, Lazar, Murphy, Castell, & Martin-Harris, 2016). In comparison to esophagram, a barium swallow is

another commonly used radiological study. According to Khan et al. (2015), a barium swallow did not result in a diagnosis of achalasia in 80% of confirmed achalasia cases (Khan et al., 2015).

Conventional esophageal manometry was the traditional test to assess patients with dysphagia before HREM became available. Conventional esophageal manometry catheters typically have five pressure sensors spaced widely apart where HREM catheters may have up to 36 pressure sensors spaced 1 cm apart (Yadlapati, 2017). As a result, HREM produces multiline tracing as well as dynamic spatiotemporal topography plots to illustrate pressure changes with different colors along length and time as opposed to conventional line tracings (Yadlapati, 2017). In a randomized, multicenter study among patients with dysphagia, investigators found HREM to be superior in earlier identification of esophageal motility disorders when compared with conventional manometry (Roman et al., 2016).

Usefulness of HREM

HREM can subtype achalasia into three clinical subclasses based on the characteristic of contractility in the body of the esophagus. Subtyping achalasia into type I to III is clinically significant, especially for patients suffering type III achalasia with a commonly reported symptom of chest pain due to esophageal spasms in distal esophagus (Moran, Lawlor, Brennan, Ravi, & Reynolds, 2015). Type III achalasia is often considered by many experts the most difficult to treat as it often presents with normal radiologic and endoscopic finding and responds poorly to all types of treatments (Khan et al., 2015; Moran et al., 2015). With HREM, essential metrics can be assessed in the diagnosis and subtyping of achalasia such as integrated relaxation pressure (IRP), LES

resting pressure, length of LES, distal esophageal pressure (DEP), pan-esophageal pressurization rate (PPR) in type II achalasia, and rate of hypercontractility in type III achalasia (Tang et al., 2015).

Treatment of Achalasia

In the past, the surgical treatment approach of achalasia involved myotomy, or cutting of the lower esophageal sphincter (LES) muscle fibers through a thoracotomy approach (Ates & Vaezi, 2015). Peroral esophageal myotomy (POEM) is an endoscopic procedure recently developed for the treatment of patients with achalasia (Ates & Vaezi, 2015). The POEM approach involves the use of an endoscope to tunnel down the distal esophagus and to cut the muscle fibers of the LES (Tang et al., 2015). Treatment decision on the length and extent of the cut along the muscle fibers depends on how high up the hypercontractile segment in the distal esophagus goes (Rohof & Bredenoord, 2017). Typically, the myotomy is about 6 cm into the esophagus and 2 cm beneath the squamocolumnar junction (Ates & Vaezi, 2015). HREM provides an effective means of assessing the exact length of involved distal esophageal segment and severity of achalasia, further supporting individualized patient management (Tang et al., 2015). It can also be used to predict the benefits and efficacy of POEM (Tang et al., 2015).

Anxiety

Anxiety has been reported to play a role in patients' healthcare experience across literature such as before cardiac imaging, diagnostic test, radiation therapy, or endoscopic procedure (Çürük, Kartın, & Kaçmaz, 2016). Patients who are anxious before a cardiac intervention often have increased basal metabolism, vasoconstriction of peripheral arteries, and elevated blood pressure due to catecholamines released in the autonomic

nervous system (Çürük et al., 2016). Furthermore, unmitigated anxiety can lead to an increase in heart rate, myocardial oxygen consumption, and myocardial contraction, as well as an increase patients' risks for arrhythmias (Ayasrah & Ahmad, 2016).

In a large multicenter study by Cisternas et al. (2017), 115 HREM studies were analyzed to appraise the correlation between different variables, including manometric variables and mood with bolus passage perception among asymptomatic individuals. The investigators concluded that there wasn't any correlation between HREM and any traditional variables except anxiety, which seemed to be a robust predictor of bolus perception, especially among asymptomatic individuals with hypotensive motility (Cisternas et al., 2017).

According to Johnson et al. (1997), expected events tend to provoke less anxiety than unexpected events. Increased predictability and an enhanced ability to understand and interpret the healthcare experience allow more energy for problem-solving or functional coping (Johnson, 1999; Melnyk & Feinstein, 2001). The use of an educational recording reduced perceived anxiety before cardiac catheterization in a randomized clinical trial by Ayasrah and Ahmad (2016). Ayasrah and Ahmad (2016) included both objectives as well as sensory information into the educational recording; sensory information includes what the patient may hear, smell, see, taste, and touch. The recording intervention had shown to be effective in decreasing anxiety before cardiac catheterization (Ayasrah & Ahmad, 2016).

Self-Regulation Theory

Preparatory education that includes descriptions of typical symptom and sensory experiences is helpful to patients as the information reduces uncertainty about the

healthcare experience and enhances coping (Christman & Cain, 2004; Johnson et al., 1997). Coping is enhanced through accurate descriptions of sensations and reductions in the discrepancy between what is expected and how the healthcare experience occurred (Melnyk & Feinstein, 2001; Johnson, 1973).

Melnyk and Feinstein (2001) studied 49 mothers and their young children, ages 24–68 months who had an unintended hospitalization in determining whether mothers' anxiety and maternal' involvement in their young children's care during hospitalization facilitated the effects of a child's behavior informational intervention. Mothers in the child behavior information group received education on the most common behavioral and emotional responses that children routinely display during and post hospitalization and as a result reported their children as having less post hospital negative behavioral change than mothers in control group (Melnyk & Feinstein, 2001). The investigators concluded that mothers who understand what behavior changes to expect in their children could create clear, explicit schemas that enable them to interpret their children's behaviors and therefore have less anxiety and able to direct emotional response to objective coping by problem-solving (Johnson, 1999; Melnyk & Feinstein, 2001).

The positive impacts of self-regulation theory-based intervention had also been demonstrated among cancer patients undergoing radiation therapy. For example, Johnson, Fieler, Wlasowicz, Mitchell, and Jones (1997) conducted a quasi-experimental study on 226 patients undergoing radiation therapy for breast or prostate cancer. The researchers found that patients who received self-regulation theory-based nursing interventions had a more positive mood and experienced less interference in their routine activities than the control group.

In addition to parental education and preparatory information for patients before treatment, self-regulation theory has also been used as a guiding framework in educational programs. Sullivan-Bolyai et al. (2014) applied the self-regulation theory as the driving framework in guiding a family-focused educational program that taught parents diabetic management for their children who are newly diagnosed with type I diabetes (Sullivan-Bolyai et al., 2014). The program included components on both functional and emotional response such as education on survival skills, visual demonstrations of signs such as what a tremor looks like; simulation with ‘hands-on’ practice and debriefing, where the visual experience is connected with the information covered to enhance the parents ability to cope with tasks such as performing a finger stick (Sullivan-Bolyai et al., 2014). The descriptions and examples of the application of theory-in-practice portrayed by the authors demonstrated the natural flow of the principles of the Self-Regulation theory with hands-on practice. How the theory can guide family-focused education in an action-oriented approach (Sullivan-Bolyai et al., 2014).

Effects of Recorded Patient Education Before Procedure

Patient education has been an integral part of many health programs, before transplants as well as pre-procedure. The effects of recorded patient education have been studied in many areas and specialties. For example, in a quality improvement project that examined the effectiveness of a multimedia education among lung transplant patients, the recorded multimedia method was more effective when preparing patients for lung transplantation as compared to standard education (Gerity, Silva, Reynolds, Hoffman, & Oermann, 2018). Specifically, patients who received the multimedia education reported

more significant gains in post-transplant knowledge ($p = 0.05$), less anxiety about the transplant surgery ($p = 0.02$), and higher satisfaction ($p = 0.02$) when compared to those receiving standard education (Gerity et al., 2018). The next part of the review of literature will explore the impact of recorded patient education on knowledge, anxiety and patient satisfaction separately.

Effects of Recorded Patient Education on Knowledge

Lattuca et al. (2018) conducted a multi-center, randomized controlled trial (RCT) evaluating the impact of an educational recording on patients' understanding, anxiety, and satisfaction before coronary angiography. Knowledge scores were higher among the intervention group (11.8 ± 2.8) as compared to control (9.5 ± 3.1) ($p < 0.001$). In another RCT by Wilson et al. (2015) evaluating the impact of a patient education recording on the understanding of cardiopulmonary resuscitation choices in the intensive care unit (ICU), investigators concluded that improvement in knowledge among the intervention group was both clinically and statistically significant ($p = 0.003$).

Not all studies demonstrate a superior impact of recorded patient education on knowledge. For example, Ferris, Condorhumaman, Waller, and Lillienthal (2015) found no differences in knowledge scores between baseline and post-op among experimental and control group in a quasi-experimental study in examining the impact of an educational recording before loop excision surgery among women in Peru. The investigators discussed that standardized translation of questionnaires maybe a limitation. However, translation was not possible due to the variation in available staff that understood Quechua and Spanish. High-quality baseline standard education may explain why there was no difference in knowledge scores between groups.

Comparable findings on knowledge were reported in a quasi-experimental study examining the effects of standardized, digitally recorded education on knowledge and anxiety in patients receiving first-time chemotherapy by Keener and Winokur (2018). In this study, there was an improvement in knowledge among all groups. The investigators concluded that both experimental and control group had increased knowledge and that this may have been due to lower baseline knowledge mean scores in the control than in the experimental group (Keener & Winokur, 2018).

Most studies demonstrated a positive impact of recorded patient education on knowledge. Several investigators discussed the strength of an educational recording as it provided standardized information to the patient (Cakmak et al., 2018; Lattuca et al., 2018; Wilson et al., 2015).

Effects of Recorded Patient Education on Anxiety

Many studies have evaluated the effects of recorded, pre-procedural education on anxiety in patients before and during examinations. There were mixed results on the impact of recorded patient education on anxiety.

In a quasi-experimental study of Taiwanese patients undergoing unsedated colonoscopy, more than 87.4% of experimental patients in the recorded education group reported that the pre-colonoscopy video helped decrease their anxiety during the colonoscopy procedure (Hsueh et al., 2016). A considerable reduction in anxiety was also evident in the quasi-experimental study by Keener and Winokur (2018). In particular, anxiety scores were lower for the intervention group on items measuring being tense and being worried ($p < 0.001$).

Cakmak et al. (2018) conducted an RCT to evaluate the effect of an education recording on anxiety and satisfaction before spinal anesthesia. The authors reported that post-op State-Trait Anxiety Inventory-Situational anxiety (STAI-S) in the intervention group was slightly lower (36.5 ± 10.0) than in the control group (39.6 ± 8.6) ($p = 0.033$). The RCT by Lattuca et al. (2018) found no difference in anxiety post-intervention between intervention group and control. The investigators reported that 77% of patients had prior information on angiography. This study was conducted in France, where universal healthcare may also explain the lack of significant difference between groups (Lattuca et al., 2018).

Ferris et al. (2015) did not evaluate anxiety but emotional state in their quasi-experimental study. The investigators found no differences in “I feel calm” among experimental group pre and post-op although post-op, the experimental group reported feeling less upset (Ferris et al., 2015). Overall, recorded patient education did not demonstrate a consistent reduction in anxiety across studies. However, the majority of the results were either positive or neutral.

Effects of Recorded Patient Education on Patient Satisfaction

Recorded patient education seemed to have a positive impact on patient satisfaction before spinal anesthesia (Cakmak et al., 2018), before coronary angiography (Lattuca et al., 2018), prior to loop excision surgery (Ferris et al., 2015), and on understanding of cardiopulmonary resuscitation choices in the ICU (Wilson et al., 2015).

Cakmak et al. (2018) evaluated the effect of an educational recording on satisfaction before spinal anesthesia with a 5-point Likert-like scale where 0 is not satisfied, and five is very satisfied. Satisfaction scores were higher in investigation group

(4.5 ± 0.6) compared to control (3.5 ± 1.2) ($p < 0.001$). Similar results were found in a study by Ferris et al. (2015) where researchers used a 3-point Likert scale where one is 'not at all satisfied' and 3 is 'much satisfaction'. In this quasi-experimental pretest and post-test study, 95% of participants liked the recording and felt the recorded education had helped them (Ferris et al., 2015). Wilson et al. (2015) also used a 3-point Likert scale in an RCT to evaluate the impact of patient education recording on the understanding of cardiopulmonary resuscitation choices in the ICU. The investigators had found that 98% of patients liked the recording, and 99% of participants would recommend the recorded education to others (Wilson et al., 2015).

Lattuca et al. (2018) used a 10-point visual analog scale (VAS) in evaluating the impact of an educational recording on patients' satisfaction before coronary angiography. In this VAS, 1 point was not satisfied, and 10 points were very satisfied. Lattuca et al. (2018) reported higher mean satisfaction score among participants in the intervention group (8.4 ± 1.9) than control (7.7 ± 2.3) ($p < 0.001$).

Recorded patient education seems to be a useful patient informational tool in improving knowledge, reducing anxiety, and increasing satisfaction. In particular, the overall impact of recorded patient education before a procedure has been positive.

METHODS

An educational digital recording about HREM for patients was developed as part of the project. Even though it is a digitally recorded education, for ease of patient understanding, the recorded patient education was referred to as a video in the teaching as well as in the questionnaires in this project. The project evaluated the effects of the recording on knowledge, procedural anxiety, satisfaction, and the abortion rate of patients undergoing the HREM procedure secondary to anxiety in the GI Motility Clinic.

Project Design

A pre-posttest design was used to evaluate knowledge, anxiety, and satisfaction levels with HREM. Baseline data was obtained from patients who received standard care which included a one-page esophageal manometry patient educational form, as well as verbal preparation from procedure nurse and physician before manometry. The implementation group received standard care plus a review of the digital recording on esophageal manometry immediately before the procedure.

Sample and Setting

A purposive, convenience sampling strategy was used and recruited 12 patients at baseline (control group) and 12 participants for implementation of the project. The setting of this project is the ambulatory GI Motility clinic within a tertiary hospital and multi-specialty academic health center in Southern California. All adult patients over the age of 18 scheduled for esophageal manometry during the project period with the ability to read and comprehend English were invited. Patients who were not able to read English or to answer pre-test and post-test questionnaires were excluded.

Educational Recording

The esophageal manometry digitally recorded education is an 8-minute educational recording for patients providing objective information about the esophageal manometry procedure. Temporal information, positioning, the sensation of pressure during the catheter insertion as well as the process of how esophageal manometry is conducted were included in the recording. This digital recording was developed by the GI Motility Clinic physicians, nurse practitioner, nurses, and staff in collaboration with the organization's patient education and nursing research departments. Filming of the digitally recorded education took place at the esophageal manometry procedural area within the GI motility clinic. This DNP project had served as the pilot for this newly developed recorded education. For the pilot, this recording was filmed in English only.

IRB and Consent

Ethical approval at the institution for this project was reviewed and deemed "not regulated" according to the organizational "Guidance to Determine if Activities Meet 'Not Regulated' Status" as set forth by the Office of Research Compliance and Quality Improvement. This project was determined to be exempt from the institutional review board (IRB) of California State University, Los Angeles (see Appendix B). An information sheet with an overview and purpose of the project were given to participants the same time pre-test questionnaires were handed out. A waiver of written consent was sought as questionnaires were answered and collected anonymously without any patient identifiers. A statement at the top of the questionnaire also stated that completion constituted agreement to participate. The digitally recorded education was shown to all patients whether or not they completed the questionnaire as this was considered the

standard method of education. There were no additional tests or interventions on the included patients other than the planned esophageal manometry procedure for which a normal procedural consent was obtained. Moreover, verbal consent was obtained from participants as recommended by the IRB.

Measures

Pre and post-test knowledge and anxiety questionnaires were administered to both control and implementation groups, while the implementation group received an additional post-test satisfaction questionnaire. The control group received standard education with the manometry preparation information sheet as well as RN and physician verbal education before the procedure. The implementation group received standard education plus the 8-minute recorded education before the procedure.

Baseline data collection started immediately after IRB approval was obtained from Cal State LA and confirmation from project site administration, but before the digital recording was developed. To make data collection more manageable, two different color papers were used for pre-test (plain), and post-test (light blue). A four-item information questionnaire in a true-false format was designed to assess knowledge of esophageal manometry before and after standard care (control group) or standard care plus watching the digitally recorded education among implementation group. Participants received 1 point for each correct answer and score was reported as a percentage. This questionnaire was developed by the doctoral student with input from specialty physicians and nurses.

Anxiety was measured by an adapted three-point Likert-type scale from an earlier article by Marteau and Bekker (1992). Marteau and Bekker (1992) developed a brief,

Six-item Short-form of State Scale of the Spielberger State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI) and this six-item Short-form has been tested and validated as compared to using the full form of the STAI. In particular, the study involved 306 participants and subjects who completed this Six-item Short-form of State Scale of STAI had similar mean scores and remained sensitive to different degrees of anxiety as compared with the full 20-item STAI (Marteau & Bekker, 1992).

The current adapted 3-item questionnaire included three anxiety items. Choice of responses is similar to that of the Six-item Short-form which ranged from “not at all” to “very much” (Marteau & Bekker, 1992). However, the number of items was reduced to three, and included both negative and positive questions such as “I feel calm” and “I am worried.” Scoring was different where a score of 4 points was given to strong negative emotions while a score of 1 point was given to positive emotions. This modified scoring method yielded total scores range from 3 – 12 where a higher score meant higher levels of anxiety and the lowest scores of 3 indicated the most relaxed emotional state. This is congruent with the items and scoring used by Keener and Winokur (2018).

A four-point satisfaction survey was used to assess patients’ satisfaction with the digital education. The satisfaction survey was adapted from a prior survey instrument from an RCT of women undergoing loop excision surgery (Ferris et al., 2015) and questions were modified to better fit the esophageal manometry population. This 4-item survey included item such as “how much did you like the video” and “do you think that other patients undergoing esophageal manometry should watch this video.” There were three possible responses each from “not at all” to “a lot.” Responses were totaled after all

questionnaires were completed and satisfaction scores were reported as percentages to each one of the three variable responses.

Procedure

Upon arrival in the clinic, in addition to normal registration forms, patients were handed the project information sheet and the plain colored pretest anxiety and knowledge questionnaire. Each pretest/posttest questionnaire had a corresponding code number. The code numbers were used to link the pretest and posttest to each other, not to the patients. No patient identifiers were placed on the questionnaires. Completed questionnaires were placed in a file at the front counter for the project lead.

For the baseline education group, education was provided after the completion of the pretest by the procedural nurse before numbing of the nose. Supplementary education was provided by the physician and patients were given opportunities to ask questions before insertion of the esophageal manometry catheter.

For the intervention group, patients were given time to complete the questionnaire prior to viewing the digitally recorded education. The digital recording was shown to the patient and family and/or significant others inside the procedural room via a pre-loaded mobile computer before starting of the routine procedural intake by the nurse. The nurse then provided standard education before application of the numbing gel to the nose. After the nose was numbed, the procedural physician entered the room and provided supplemental education. The participants were given an opportunity to ask questions about the HREM before giving the informed consent for the procedure.

After the procedure, patients who had completed the questionnaire pre-procedure were offered the opportunity to complete the light blue colored post questionnaire with

the added satisfaction information. Completed post surveys were placed in a separate file next to the pretest.

Data Analysis

Knowledge, anxiety, and satisfaction data were entered into IBM Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) Statistics, version 25.0 by the project lead. SPSS was used to generate descriptive statistics and determine associations among variables. A crosstabs procedure will be used to create two-dimensional frequency distribution among variables.

Summary of Methods

This DNP project served as the pilot for this newly developed digitally recorded education about HREM. The adapted anxiety short-form with modified three-items questionnaires and the overall pre and post-tests are meant to be simple and concise. These brief questionnaires with 11-items total should take less than five minutes to complete and are predicted to help maximize recruitment and response rate. The data analysis plan involves descriptive statistics, which were used to evaluate the clinical significance of the project.

RESULTS

A total of 24 participants completed the questionnaires (12 baseline education group and 12 implementation group). Descriptive statistics for all variables obtained at baseline, pre and post-questionnaires for both groups are displayed in Table 1 to 4. Due to the anonymous nature of this project, patient demographics are not available.

Knowledge

There was a significant increase in knowledge in both the control (mean increase from 2.4 to 3.8 out of 4 (60% to 95%) and implementation group (mean increase from 2.3 to 3.8 out of 4 (58% to 95%) after receiving education. There was no significant difference in the mean baseline knowledge scores (2.4 vs. 2.3) and the mean knowledge improvement score between the two groups (3.8 vs 3.8). These findings indicated that in this sample the digital teaching was as effective as standard education. T-tests were not performed on the current sample because the sample size was too small.

When examining each knowledge score separately, 33% of participants in the control group were able to answer the question “The esophageal manometry procedure takes 1 hour to complete” correctly pre-education. Significant improvement in knowledge score was seen clinically as 100% of patients were able to get the same question right post standard education (Table 1). A similar but less significant result was seen in the implementation group where 25% of patients were able to answer the same question correctly pre-education, and 83% got the right answer post digital education (Table 2).

Table 1

Results on Knowledge for Control Group

Knowledge Control Group	Pre N = 12		Post N = 12	
	Correct	Incorrect	Correct	Incorrect
The esophageal manometry procedure takes 1 hour to complete	33% (4)	67% (8)	100% (12)	0% (0)
The manometry catheter will be inserted first with my head in a normal position	58% (7)	42% (5)	92% (11)	8% (1)
The esophageal manometry is done while I am asleep	67% (8)	33% (4)	92% (11)	8% (1)
I can drive after esophageal manometry procedure	83% (10)	17% (2)	100% (12)	0% (0)

On the other hand, 100% of the implementation group were able to answer all three other knowledge questions correctly as compared to 95% of patients got the other three questions correct in the control group. Specifically, 11 out of 12 of the control group got the answer to “the manometry catheter will be inserted first with my head in a normal position” and “the esophageal manometry is done while I am asleep” right in compared to all patients got the correct answers in the implementation group.

The greatest knowledge deficit based on pre-educational knowledge scores seemed to fall on timing of procedure where 67% of patients in the control group and 75% of participants in the implementation group did not know the procedure takes less than 1 hour to complete. The remarkable improvement in both the specific item and total knowledge scores among participants in both control and implementation groups suggested that both standard education and digital recorded education are effective in improving knowledge before esophageal manometry procedure.

Table 2

Results on Knowledge for Implementation Groups

Knowledge Implementation Group	Pre N = 12		Post N = 12	
	Correct	Incorrect	Correct	Incorrect
The esophageal manometry procedure takes 1 hour to complete	25% (3)	75% (9)	83% (10)	17% (2)
The manometry catheter will be inserted first with my head in a normal position	58% (7)	42% (5)	100% (12)	0% (0)
The esophageal manometry is done while I am asleep	83% (10)	17% (2)	100% (12)	0% (0)
I can drive after esophageal manometry procedure	67% (8)	33% (4)	100% (12)	0% (0)

Anxiety

Both standard and recorded education were effective in reducing patients' anxiety. There was a meaningful reduction of anxiety scores in both the control (mean reduction from 7.1 to 5.5 out of 12) and implementation group (mean reduction from 8.25 to 7.16 out of 12). Comparable decrease in median anxiety scores was also seen among the control group (median reduction of 7 to 5.5 out of 12) and implementation group (median reduction of 8.5 to 7 out of 12).

When evaluating each item scores for anxiety separately, "I feel calm" saw the greatest improvement among both groups. In particular, there was a mean reduction of anxiety score of 0.58 out of 4 in the control group and 0.50 out of 4 in the implementation group. This is equivalent to 15% and 13% of improved emotional state with patients feeling more calm after standard teaching (Table 3) and digitally recorded education (Table 4).

Table 3

Results on Anxiety for Control Group

Anxiety Control Group	Mean \pm Standard Deviation	
	Pre-Education	Post-Education
I feel calm	2.75 \pm 0.97	2.17 \pm 1.03
I am tense	2.25 \pm 0.97	1.83 \pm 0.58
I am worried	2.08 \pm 1.08	1.5 \pm 0.52

Table 4

Results on Anxiety for Implementation Group

Anxiety Implementation Group	Mean \pm Standard Deviation	
	Pre-Education	Post-Education
I feel calm	3.0 \pm 1.04	2.5 \pm 0.91
I am tense	2.58 \pm 0.90	2.33 \pm 0.99
I am worried	2.67 \pm 0.89	2.33 \pm 0.78

Satisfaction

All participants liked the recorded education and rated satisfaction level at “some” or “a lot” on all 4-items of the questionnaires (Table 5). In particular, 83% of patients reported that the educational recording had helped them and that the recorded education helped answer their questions about the esophageal manometry procedure. The lowest mean score for satisfaction was 2.75 out of 3, while the highest was 3.0. 100% of patients indicated that other patients undergoing esophageal manometry should watch this recorded education.

Table 5

Patients Rating of the Video

Item	Variable	N	%	Mean	SD
How Well did the video help answer your questions about the procedure?	A lot	10	83	2.83	0.39
	Some	2	17		
	Not at all	0	0		
How much did you like the video?	A lot	9	75	2.75	0.45
	Some	3	25		
	Not at all	0	0		
Do you think that other patients undergoing esophageal manometry should watch this video?	No	0	0	3.00	0.39
	Yes	12	100		
How much did the video help you?	A lot	10	83	2.83	0.39
	Some	2	17		
	Not at all	0	0		

Procedural abortion rate

A four-week period immediately before implementation served as the baseline data period to determine procedural abortion rate. During the four weeks, the GI Motility clinic recorded two out of 24 (8%) esophageal manometry procedures that were terminated due to heightened anxiety. Both of these patients aborted the procedures during insertion of esophageal manometry catheters. Throughout the implementation period, moderate to high levels of anxiety had been reported, and zero out of 24 procedures was aborted.

DISCUSSION

The results of this project appear to support the positive impact of recorded patient education as evidenced in the greater literature. While the digital education did not show greater increases in knowledge scores or lower anxiety scores as compared to standard education, there was a substantial increase in both the knowledge scores and reduction in anxiety scores post-recorded education. Therefore, both standard teaching and digital education proved to be effective in improving knowledge and reducing anxiety.

While it is possible that nurses were providing quality education to all patients before esophageal manometry, the potential of a Hawthorne effect, or the consequence of the nurses being aware of being studied and thus enriched the teaching during study period should be considered (McCambridge, Witton, & Elbourne, 2014). Additionally, the small sample size may have impacted results. Given a longer timeframe for baseline collection, additional differences may have appeared. However, both the baseline data collection period and the digitally recorded education period were truncated when HREM procedures were stopped for several months, due to COVID-19 restrictions.

Digitally recorded education offers the benefit of a standard method of teaching, a factor that has been cited in the literature as beneficial (Cakmak et al., 2018; Lattuca et al., 2018; Wilson et al., 2015). Thus, this standard education reduces potential biases while preserving quality education before esophageal manometry.

All project participants liked the recorded education and recommended that other patients undergoing esophageal manometry should watch it. The GI Motility Clinic's quarterly procedural patient satisfaction scores is currently pending. A preliminary

review revealed a score of 96%, which is a significant improvement from the score of 89% before project implementation.

In addition to high satisfaction, the GI Motility clinic also had no aborted procedures during the project implementation period. This is a potential cost saving because the majority of the aborted cases due to heightened anxiety were cancelled after or during manometry catheter insertion, after all equipment was opened or used. Reducing potential aborted cases or to be able to cancel a procedure before opening of sterile supplies can reduce potential non-reimbursable cost to re-sterilize equipment and replace opened, but unused resources. Additionally, cancelling a case due to anxiety can lead to negative patient satisfaction scores. Ashton, Hamid, Sulieman, Eardley, and Baker (2017) conducted a study in examining factors influencing elective surgical patients' experience and satisfaction after surgical management of ankle fractures. The investigators found that patients whom got cancelled were reported to be less satisfied (VAS score of 7 out of 10) as compared to patients who were not cancelled (VAS score of 9 out of 10) ($p = 0.005$) (Ashton et al., 2017).

Limitations

Several limitations existed in this project. First is that the sample size in this pilot was very small. One of the key reasons for the very small sample size was due to limited time for implementation of the project secondary to Covid-19. This impacted the review and approval of the patient educational recording, as well as deferring elective procedures by the organization during the pandemic. Elective procedures such as esophageal manometry were placed on hold from mid-March, 2020 until mid-May, 2020 based on surge measures restrictions from the Los Angeles County Department of Public Health

and Executive Order N-33-20 by the governor which required residents of California to stay at home. (Los Angeles County Department of Public Health, 2020). Moreover, the organization prioritized urgent cases only during initial re-opening of elective procedures to allowed sufficient time for disinfection and social distancing in the patient waiting area. The number of procedures was reduced to about 30% of usual caseloads during the reopening phase. As a result, a very small sample size was obtained. This project will be continued at the institution following this initial phase. It is projected that the information about the efficacy of the recorded education will improve as the sample size gets larger. No additional information will be collected in the control group because all patients now receive the recorded information.

A second limitation of this project was regarding the newly created patient educational recording. Several areas of the educational recording have been found to be in need of improvement. One was that the audio volume was too low, despite being adjusted to maximal setting. This was further complicated by the background noise made by the manometry device in the procedural room. The project team tried to modify the environment by having the patients watch the recording from another room without the machine. However, an extra clinic room was only available for a limited time and may not be sufficient for completion of the 8-minute recorded education. Using an audio speaker could be another modifier to improve the sound quality in the future.

An additional barrier was that the digital recording is available in English only. Therefore, it excluded potential patients who underwent the procedure but who were not able to comprehend English. A prospective development of the recording in additional languages such as Spanish may be possible in collaboration with the patient education

committee later as resources become available. Lastly, the educational recording and its implementation aimed at patients undergoing esophageal manometry and cannot be generalized to other types of manometry or procedures.

Implications for Practice

Quality digital education before esophageal manometry plays a pivotal role in improving knowledge, reducing anxiety, increasing satisfaction, and reducing procedural abortion rate secondary to anxiety. Moreover, the significant increase in knowledge (from 58% to 95%) and reduction in anxiety (mean reduction in anxiety score from 8.25 to 7.16 out of 12 or 9%) post recorded education suggested potential project success with implementation of digital education before esophageal manometry procedure. Continued study with a larger sample size is needed. Lessons learned from this project include improving audio or use of a sound system and providing the recorded education in additional languages other than English. These can be used to guide the development of future projects. This project can also help direct future developments or patient digitally recorded educational in other settings to provide a standardized means of patient education and improve patient outcome.

Conclusion

The GI Motility team had created a digital educational recording to provide objective, temporal, and concrete information about the esophageal manometry procedure. This DNP project demonstrated that recorded education was effective in improving knowledge, reducing anxiety, increasing patient satisfaction, and decreasing procedural abortion rate. Findings from this project would support the larger body of evidence showing a positive impact of recorded patient education on patient outcomes.

REFERENCES

- Ashton, F., Hamid, K., Sulieman, S., Eardley, W., & Baker, P. (2017). Factors influencing patient experience and satisfaction following surgical management of ankle fractures. *Injury*, *48*(4), 960-965. doi:10.1016/j.injury.2017.02.017
- Ates, F., & Vaezi, M. F. (2015). The pathogenesis and management of achalasia: Current status and future directions. *Gut and Liver*, *9*(4)449-463. doi:10.5009/gnl14446
- Ayasrah, S. M., & Ahmad, M. M. (2016). Educational video intervention effects on periprocedural anxiety levels among cardiac catheterization patients: A randomized clinical trial. *Research and Theory for Nursing Practice*, *30*(1), 70-84. doi:10.1891/1541-6577.30.1.70
- Cakmak, M., Kose, I., Zincircioglu, C., Karaman, Y., Tekgul, Z., Pektas, S., . . . Bozkurt, P. S. (2018). Effect of video-based education on anxiety and satisfaction of patients undergoing spinal anesthesia. *Revista Brasileira De Anestesiologia*, *68*(3), 274-279. doi:10.1016/j.bjane.2018.01.004
- Cameron, L. D., & Leventhal, H. (2008). *The self-regulation of health and illness behaviour*. London, UK: Routledge.
- Carleton, R. N. (2016). Fear of the unknown: One fear to rule them all? *Journal of Anxiety Disorders*, *41*, 5-21. doi:10.1016/j.janxdis.2016.03.011
- Carlson, D. A., Omari, T., Lin, Z., Rommel, N., Starkey, K., Kahrilas, P. J., . . . Pandolfino, J. E. (2016). High-resolution impedance manometry parameters enhance the esophageal motility evaluation in non-obstructive dysphagia patients without a major Chicago Classification motility disorder. *Neurogastroenterology & Motility*, *29*(3), 1-25. doi:10.1111/nmo.12941

- Christman, N. J., & Cain, L. B. (2004). The effects of concrete objective information and relaxation on maintaining usual activity during radiation therapy. *Oncology Nursing Forum*, 31(2), E39-45. doi:10.1188/04.onf.e39-e45
- Cisternas, D., Scheerens, C., Omari, T., Monrroy, H., Hani, A., Leguizamo, A., . . . Serra, J. (2017). Anxiety can significantly explain bolus perception in the context of hypotensive esophageal motility: Results of a large multicenter study in asymptomatic individuals. *Neurogastroenterology & Motility*, 29(9), 1-10. doi:10.1111/nmo.13088
- Çürük, G. N., Kartın, P. T., & Kaçmaz, H. Y. (2016). Examination of the anxiety level in patients undergoing transesophageal echocardiography. *Echocardiography*, 33(12), 1860-1865. doi:10.1111/echo.13366
- Ferris, D. G., Condorhuaman, W. S., Waller, J., & Lilienthal, A. (2015). Impact of a video intervention for rural Peruvian women with cervical neoplasia before loop excisional procedures. *Journal of Lower Genital Tract Disease*, 19(3), 224-228.
- Gaumnitz, E. A. (2019, February 02). Esophageal motility disorders. Retrieved February 2, 2019, from <https://emedicine.medscape.com/article/174783-overview#a6>doi:10.1097/lgt.0000000000000107
- Hsueh, F., Chen, C., Sun, C., Chou, Y., Hsiao, S., & Yang, T. (2016). A study on the effects of a health education intervention on anxiety and pain during colonoscopy procedures. *Journal of Nursing Research*, 24(2), 181-189. doi:10.1097/jnr.0000000000000112

- Ihara, E., Muta, K., Fukaura, K., & Nakamura, K. (2017). Diagnosis and treatment strategy of achalasia subtypes and esophagogastric junction outflow obstruction based on high-resolution manometry. *Digestion*, *95*(1), 29-35.
doi:10.1159/000452354
- Johnson, J. E. (1973). Effects of accurate expectations about sensations on the sensory and distress components of pain. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, *27*(2), 261-275. doi:10.1037/h0034767
- Johnson, J. E. (1996). Coping with radiation therapy: Optimism and the effect of preparatory interventions. *Research in Nursing & Health*, *19*(1), 3-12.
doi:10.1002/(sici)1098-240x(199602)19:13.0.co;2-s
- Johnson, J. E. (1999). Self-regulation theory and coping with physical illness. *Research in Nursing & Health*, *22*(6), 435-448.
doi:10.1002/(sici)1098240x(199912)22:63.3.co;2-h
- Johnson, J. E., Fieler, V. K., Jones, L. S., Wlasowicz, G. S., & Mitchell, M. L. (1997). *Self-regulation theory: Applying theory to your practice*. Pittsburgh, PA: Oncology Nursing Press.
- Johnson, J. E., Fieler, V. K., Wlasowicz, G. S., Michell, M. L., & Jones, L. S. (1997). The effects of nursing care guided by self-regulation theory on coping with radiation therapy. *Oncology Nursing Forum*, *24*(6), 1041-50.
doi:10.1002/(sici)1098-240x(199912)22:63.3.co;2-h

- Kahrilas, P. J., Bredenoord, A. J., Fox, M., Gyawali, C. P., Roman, S., Smout, A. J., & Pandolfino, J. E. (2014). The Chicago Classification of esophageal motility disorders, v3.0. *Neurogastroenterology & Motility*, 27(2), 160-174.
doi:10.1111/nmo.12477
- Keener, K., & Winokur, E. J. (2018). Digitally recorded education: Effects on anxiety and knowledge recall in patients receiving first-time chemotherapy. *Clinical Journal of Oncology Nursing*, 22(4), 444-449. doi:10.1188/18.cjon.444-449
- Khan, M., Alqaraawi, A., Al-Sohaibani, F., Al-Kahtani, K., & Al-Ashgar, H. (2015). Clinical, endoscopic, and radiologic features of three subtypes of achalasia, classified using high-resolution manometry. *Saudi Journal of Gastroenterology*, 21(3), 152-157. doi:10.4103/1319-3767.157560
- Kurlander, J. E., Sondhi, A. R., Waljee, A. K., Menees, S. B., Connell, C. M., Schoenfeld, P. S., & Saini, S. D. (2016). How efficacious are patient education interventions to improve bowel preparation for colonoscopy? A systematic review. *Plos One*, 11(10). doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0164442
- Lattuca, B., Barber-Chamoux, N., Alos, B., Sfaxi, A., Mulliez, A., Miton, N., . . . Bouleti, C. (2018). Impact of video on the understanding and satisfaction of patients receiving informed consent before elective inpatient coronary angiography: A randomized trial. *American Heart Journal*, 200, 67-74.
doi:10.1016/j.ahj.2018.03.00

- Los Angeles County Department of Public Health. (2020, May 08). Novel Coronavirus (COVID-19) Los Angeles County Department of Public Health. *Resuming Deferred and Preventive Health Care in Los Angeles County*, 1-5. Retrieved June 18, 2020, from <http://publichealth.lacounty.gov/acd/docs/resumingcare.pdf>
- Maggio, L. A., Sewell, J. L., & Artino, A. R. (2016, July). *The literature review: A foundation for high-quality Medical Education Research*. Retrieved April 14, 2019, from <https://jgme.org/doi/full/10.4300/JGME-D-16-00175.1>
- Marteau, T. M., & Bekker, H. (1992, September). The development of a six-item short-form of the state scale of the Spielberger State-Trait Anxiety Inventory (STAI). Retrieved May 1, 2019, from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/1393159>
- McCambridge, J., Witton, J., & Elbourne, D. R. (2014). Systematic review of the Hawthorne effect: New concepts are needed to study research participation effects. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*, *67*(3), 267-277.
doi:10.1016/j.jclinepi.2013.08.015
- Melnyk, B. M., & Feinstein, N. F. (2001). Mediating functions of maternal anxiety and participation in care on young childrens' posthospital adjustment. *Research in Nursing & Health*, *24*(1), 18-26. doi:10.1002/1098-240x(200102)24:13.0.co;2-5
- Mosleh, S., Eshah, N., & Darawad, M. (2016). Percutaneous coronary intervention and heart surgery learning needs of patients in Jordan. *International Nursing Review*, *63*(4), 562-571. doi:10.1111/inr.12318

- O'Rourke, A. K., Lazar, A., Murphy, B., Castell, D. O., & Martin-Harris, B. (2016). Utility of esophagram versus high-resolution manometry in the detection of esophageal dysmotility. *Otolaryngology–Head and Neck Surgery*, *154*(5), 888-891. doi:10.1177/0194599816629379
- Reddy, C. A., Patel, A., & Gyawali, C. P. (2017). Impact of esophageal motor diagnoses on symptom burden and health-related quality of life (HRQOL). *Neurogastroenterology and Motility*, *29*(4), 1-17. doi:10.1111/nmo.12970
- Rohof, W. O., & Bredenoord, A. J. (2017). Chicago classification of esophageal motility disorders: Lessons learned. *Current Gastroenterology Reports*, *19*(8).
- Roman, S., Huot, L., Zerbib, F., Varannes, S. B., Gourcerol, G., Coffin, B., . . . Mion, F. (2016). High-Resolution manometry improves the diagnosis of esophageal motility disorders in patients with dysphagia: A randomized multicenter study. *American Journal of Gastroenterology*, *111*(3), 372-380. doi:10.1038/ajg.2016.1
- Sullivan-Bolyai, S., Johnson, K., Cullen, K., Hamm, T., Bisordi, J., Blaney, K., . . . Melkus, G. (2014). Tried and true. *Advances in Nursing Science*, *37*(4), 340-349. doi:10.1097/ans.0000000000000050
- Tang, Y., Xie, C., Wang, M., Jiang, L., Shi, R., & Lin, L. (2015). Association of high-resolution manometry metrics with the symptoms of achalasia and the symptomatic outcomes of peroral esophageal myotomy. *Plos One*, *10*(9). doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0139385

Wilson, M. E., Krupa, A., Hinds, R. F., Litell, J. M., Swetz, K. M., Akhouni, A., . . .

Kashani, K. (2015). A video to improve patient and surrogate understanding of cardiopulmonary resuscitation choices in the ICU. *Critical Care Medicine*, 43(3), 621-629. doi:10.1097/ccm.000000000000074

Yadlapati, R. (2017). High-resolution esophageal manometry. *Current Opinion in Gastroenterology*, 33(4), 301-309. doi:10.1097/mog.0000000000000369

APPENDIX A

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INFORMATION ABOUT REQUESTOR:

Name: Coka Yip

Company or institution: California State University Fullerton (DNP student)

Street address: 5557 W. 6th Street 1-108

City: Los Angeles **State:** CA **Zip/postal code:** 90036 **Country:** USA

Phone number: 586 612 2994

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Coka Yip

Print Name

Job Title: NP

Date: 3/18/2019 | 12:49 PM EDT

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 Lori Brown, Chief Experience Officer (Licensor)

Lori Brown

Print Name

Date: 3/19/2019 | 10:32 AM EDT

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APPENDIX B
CSULA IRB APPROVAL

Office Memorandum

DATE:	January 29, 2020
TO:	Elizabeth Winokur
FROM:	Elia Amaro
PROJECT TITLE:	[1524426-1] Effects of Digitally Recorded Patient Education Before Esophageal Manometry Procedure
REFERENCE #:	19-87X
SUBMISSION TYPE:	New Project
ACTION:	DETERMINATION OF EXEMPT STATUS
DECISION DATE:	January 29, 2020
REVIEW CATEGORY:	Exemption category # 2(i)

Thank you for your submission of New Project materials for this project. The California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB has determined that this project is EXEMPT FROM IRB REVIEW according to federal regulations.

We will retain a copy of this correspondence within our records.

IF ANY CHANGES ARE MADE TO THE METHODS AND PROCEDURES DESCRIBED IN THIS PROTOCOL, YOU MUST SUBMIT A MODIFICATION APPLICATION SO THAT THE PROJECT MAY BE RE-EVALUATED FOR EXEMPTION FROM IRB REVIEW.

For any inquiries about this project, please use the Send Project Mail option on IRBNet to contact Elia Amaro. **It allows us to keep all correspondence related to this project in one place, rather than scattered between IRBNet and emails.**

This letter has been electronically signed in accordance with all applicable regulations, and a copy is retained within California State University, Los Angeles (Cal State LA) IRB's records.

APPENDIX C

CSMC ENDORSEMENT LETTER

Date: October 25, 2019

To: Elizabeth Winokur, PhD, RN Team Leader/Chair
Cinthy Sotelo, DNP, FNP-C Team Member
Southern California CSU DNP Consortium
California State University, LA
5151 State University Drive
Los Angeles, CA 90032

Subj: Endorsement of Coka Yip, DNP student letter;

Effects of Digitally Recorded Patient Education Before Esophageal Manometry Procedure

This letter of endorsement confirms our support of Ms. Coka Yip's quality improvement project as part of her Doctor of Nursing Practice education entitled. The project is entitled, Effects of Digitally Recorded Patient Education Before Esophageal Manometry Procedure at our GI Motility Clinic.

After careful review of the above-referenced proposal, this project may begin following Institutional Review Board determination at California State University, LA. We will guide Ms. Yip through any required IRB review at Cedars-Sinai. In addition, Ms. Coka Yip will have guidance and support from our Nursing Research team, Patient Education staff, as well as access to pertinent data related to the project. No identifiable patient data may be used during the completion of this project. Also, you may not remove any physical form of data from the facility.

If there are any substantial changes to your protocol or procedures before or during the conduct of your project, a new project proposal must be submitted for approval.

Regards,

Harriet Udin Aronow, PhD
Research Scientist IV
Professor, Medicine and Biomedical Sciences
Nursing Research Department

APPENDIX D
INFORMATION LETTER

Information Letter: Effects of Digitally Recorded Patient Education Before Esophageal
Manometry Procedure

To Project Participant:

You are invited to take part in a research project conducted by Coka Yip, MSN, RN, A Doctorate of Nursing practice student at California State University, Los Angeles and her faculty chair, Elizabeth Winokur, PhD, RN. In this study, we hope to learn more about the impact of education on knowledge and anxiety related to manometry procedures.

Our GI Motility team has created a short educational video for you to watch before your esophageal manometry procedure today. We are trying to assess the helpfulness of the video to see if there is any need change the education in the future. You were selected to participate in this study because you are here for the esophageal manometry procedure during our study recruitment period.

Participants will be expected to fill out a pre-test and post-test questionnaires before and after watching the video today. The survey takes less than 5 minutes to complete and you can fill it out while you are waiting in the pre-procedural area. We hope that our research will lead to an improvement of patient's knowledge about esophageal manometry, decrease procedural anxiety, and to improve patient satisfaction.

Participation is voluntary. You will be watching the same video as others regardless whether you decide to take part in the study or not. The care you receive will also be the same. There is no compensation for participating.

The risk of loss of confidentiality is very low in this study as we ask that you do not write your name or any other identifier on the questionnaire. All questionnaires will be anonymous. You will see a code on the top of the prequestionnaire and post-questionnaire; this code is to link the surveys together and not to identify you or other patients in this study. Reports from this study will not identify you as a participant. All information gathered in this study will remain confidential and be given out only with your permission or as required by law.

If you have any questions about this research at any time, please call Elizabeth Winokur, PhD, RN, CEN at 714-4024270 or write her at ewinok2@calstatela.edu or 5151 State University Dr., Los Angeles. You may also contact or yipcoka@csu.fullerton.edu

By participating in this study you indicate that you have read the form and agree voluntarily to participate. If you choose not to take part there will be no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are entitled. If you agree to take part, you are free to withdraw from it at any time. Likewise, no penalty or loss of benefits to which you are otherwise entitled will occur.

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH

APPENDIX E

PRE-TEST QUESTIONNAIRES

Please complete before you view the educational video. Completion of the questionnaires constitutes agreement to participate. Please do not put your name or identifier on this test.

Knowledge: Please circle true or false for each statement.

1. The esophageal manometry procedure takes about 1 hour to complete	True	False
2. The manometry catheter will be inserted first with my head in a normal position	True	False
3. The esophageal manometry is done while I am asleep	True	False
4. I can drive after esophageal manometry procedure	True	False

Anxiety: Please circle the one correspondence that represents your current emotion the most for each row.

I feel calm	Not at all	Somewhat	Moderately	Very much
I am tense	Not at all	Somewhat	Moderately	Very much
I am worried	Not at all	Somewhat	Moderately	Very much

Thank you for participating, please turn in completed questionnaires to our procedural nurses or staffs at the front counter.

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH.

APPENDIX F

POST-TEST QUESTIONNAIRES

Please complete the following after you viewed the educational video. Completion of the questionnaires constitutes agreement to participate. Please do not put your name or identifier on this test.

Knowledge: Please circle true or false for each statement.

1. The esophageal manometry procedure takes about 1 hour to complete	True	False
2. The manometry catheter will be inserted first with my head in a normal position	True	False
3. The esophageal manometry is done while I am asleep	True	False
4. I can drive after esophageal manometry procedure	True	False

Anxiety: Please circle the one correspondence that represents your current emotion the most for each row.

I feel calm	Not at all	Somewhat	Moderately	Very much
I am tense	Not at all	Somewhat	Moderately	Very much
I am worried	Not at all	Somewhat	Moderately	Very much

Satisfaction: Please circle the one correspondence that represents your satisfaction level the most.

1. How well did the video help answer your questions about the procedure?	A lot Some Not at all
2. How much did you like the video?	A lot Some Not at all
3. Do you think that other patients undergoing esophageal manometry should watch this video?	No Yes
4. How much did the video help you?	A lot Some Not at all

Any additional feedback or suggestion to help us improve the way we prepare patients for the esophageal manometry?

Thank you for participating, please turn in completed questionnaires to our procedural nurses or staffs at the front counter.

THIS PROJECT HAS BEEN DETERMINED TO BE EXEMPT FROM REVIEW AND APPROVAL BY THE CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, LOS ANGELES INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD FOR THE PROTECTION OF HUMAN SUBJECTS IN RESEARCH.